

THE ISSUE OF USING TRANSLATION IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: This article assumes that foreign language teaching and translation activities should be interrelated in the training of foreign language specialists. The article also gives practical suggestions based on the results of field studies based on the methodology of teaching translation in foreign language classes and the importance of developing evaluation criteria.

Key words: foreign language teaching methodology, grammatical translation, behaviorism, skills and abilities, evaluation criteria.

Introduction

Language teaching in the current period of learning foreign languages development of methods, improvement of existing ones, old methods processes such as updating are gaining momentum. Teaching foreign languages It is necessary to improve the methodology of language acquisition serves to develop skills. To teach foreign languages in most cases, the requirements are aimed at developing four skills: listening, speaking, reading and writing skills. It should be noted that it is the largest in foreign language learning translation skills are a bit out of the question scored Translation studies as a separate linguistic science considered, foreign languages are slowly applied to the educational process. Saying

It is possible that such a situation can be observed all over the world and this problem scientists tried to find a solution as a result of their studies. G. Cook "fifth skill" of translation (speaking, listening, writing and along with reading)

emphasizes the idea and attributes it to Friedrich L. Venuti translation is not just a form of linguistic transcoding, but emphasizes that it is a creative activity.

During several years of our pedagogical activity, the direction of philology most of the graduates have little skills in literary translation we watched him limp. The main reason for this is translation to students The theory is not given enough, even if it is given, it is wide in practice not applicable, even if applicable, according to translation criteria we know that it is not appreciated. A group of researchers led by A. Pim 878 from ten countries language as a result of a survey conducted among language teachers teachers do not like translation, the most popular education the method of giving is "communicative approach" and the least and determines that the one used is "grammatical translation". This therefore, from the language teacher's methodology and preferred approach therefore, the practice of translation is not widely used in the educational process.

In fact, a modern linguist is a grammarian in the studies of pedagogues a negative relationship with translation is observed. Grammatical translation It was the dominant teaching method in language classes until the 1940s. In this, reading and writing are the main focus, and translation exercises lexis and grammar by referring to the student's mother tongue used for learning. Grammar in the translation activity in the mother tongue communication with speakers, speaking and listening skills acquisition is not seen as the goal of language teaching.

Another traditional method in language teaching is behavioral approach, language learning theories in the 1950s and 1960s turned to behaviorism, that is, learning that views language acquisition as habit formation based on the theory. Naturally, in language teaching, understanding a foreign language discourse or text, more emphasis is placed on increasing vocabulary. Memorized words work on native language equivalents and alternatives is much slower.

As well as strengthening each new word during the learning process For this purpose, the experience of translating the text word for word is widely observed. As a result, students have a habit of translating word for word is formed. S. Kolina

involved in behavioristic/contrastive methodology done that students learn knowledge of language rather than how to use it, not to create or share meaningful information, J.Holmes translation activities alongside language learning, with him language as an area that can potentially work together in dialogue obtained. Therefore, learning a foreign language is not about translation

We believe that it cannot be carried out in this way. By the way, with this claim specifically, the course, direction, on the training of foreign language specialists, we mean specialties. It is known that there is a big difference between the mother tongue and the foreign language being studied

there are differences, and these differences are cultural differences, worldviews, It is caused by the landscape of lifestyle and concepts. That's it to overcome the differences and render it correctly and adequately in the translation and requires linguistic and non-linguistic knowledge from the translator.

According to A. Pym, in the 1980s and early 1990s learning more than two languages to translate it was said that translation competence is more important than knowledge of the language was more important. Language training itself to train translators there was a lot of emphasis on its inadequacy our vision of translation expands, literature, anthropology, culture, philosophy and political explores the central role of translation in understanding sociology and students are not only translators, but also writers, editors, publishers and projects expands future prospects as managers. From this it seems that the translation activity requires the student to master a large encyclopedic knowledge in addition to the foreign language and the mother tongue, and as a result the professional perspective of the emerging specialist will be wide.

Current trends in language teaching (SLA research based on the results) and the training of translators is general communicative aimed at developing communication skills. Communicative the goal of language teaching is acquisition of communicative competence, i.e be able to express, interpret and discuss content is to help.

Ten examples from the 2013 study by A. Pym et al Finland, People's Republic of China as a result of country studies and teachers in countries like Great Britain about translation in France, Spain and Germany, which has expressed a lot of opinions and Oz they watch what is said. The interesting thing about this distribution is that 2012- EF English Proficiency Index (EF English Proficiency Index) according to the data, to the best results in learning English Some countries that have achieved this are also high in the use of translation those with grades. For example, Finland is on both lists takes first place.

From the above information, translation activities in foreign language classes We can see how important it is to apply. Current with only language teaching in the context of global intercultural exchanges cannot be limited. Understanding language is different, expressed in it is different, it's another to embrace a specific cultural aspect. These are the peculiarities and for understanding, the formation of translation skills in students and we think it should be deleted. Also, not only in a foreign language, but also in his own it is necessary to pay attention to increasing the vocabulary in the mother tongue. Education organize the process 1st year of bachelor's degree abroad words in the exercises mainly with the translation option from the native language dictionary if it is given, in the 2nd year, students will be introduced to the environment of a foreign language, in which

It is important to explain the words in a foreign language, not in the native language according to From the 3rd and 4th years, it is determined according to the curriculum translation theory and most of the basic foreign language classes should be put into practice. full integration of translation activities in foreign language classes in courses should be, in which the students are actualizing their language skills emphasizes that they can be used in communicative contexts.

How to introduce translation into foreign language classes and methods The opinions of a number of scholars regarding the need to develop translation methodology helps out. In particular, A. Pym: "Students spontaneously, in real life or role we should encourage translation in the medium of play. Different to

students we should give translations and then discuss the differences. Thus, each phrase in a foreign language has only one translation option for the phrase we give up the idea that there is. Because of this translation to students we need to allow adding and removing content during the process." says. According to this proposal, we students languages and cultures we make it possible to identify and study many differences between

The use of translation in teaching foreign languages is given to students in one gator with translation skills, understanding the task in his native language adopts analytical or verbal-linguistic learning strategies. Translation to the method used by the teacher in the course of training adapt and create opportunities for students to communicate freely possible Translation is used in foreign language teaching nowadays to meet the demands and needs of language teaching should be adapted. L.Venuti to encourage the study of a foreign language and translation together from social constructivist theory during classroom activities indicates the need to use. In this, students are in project work they play the role of editor, coordinator and terminologist. Translation encourage cooperation and dialogue in solving their problems students' critical attitude to their teammate's translation on the basis of which their discussion and evaluation actions are carried out.

It should be noted that foreign language classes are carried out by students increased translations must be evaluated according to certain criteria. Translation in students as a result of adequate criticism and assessment skill development is inevitable. M. Melis Evaluation of translation in three directions of translation: edition evaluation of completed translations, evaluation of the work of professional translators and showed that assessment in translation teaching is relevant. Students assessment is a translation product and an individual process carried out (adherence to relevant principles). Translation product quality, and quantity (work) can be estimated. In this field three functions of assessment (diagnostic, summative and formative) works. Translations for evaluation, evaluation criteria, evaluation and correction scales, questionnaires, exercises, etc. are required.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that in teaching a foreign language the ability to translate students' language skills into a criterion must also be entered separately. Training foreign language specialists to a positive effect in improving communicative communication skills methodology of teaching translation activities, methodology, independent development of educational forms and assessment criteria is worthwhile.

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